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NEAR FIELD COMMUNICATION-SAFETY AND SECURITY

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Abstract-

NFC (near field communication) is a standards-based, short-range wireless connectivity technology that enables simple and intuitive two-way interactions between electronic devices. It is very convenient to touch and communicate between two NFC devices. For example, with smart phone-integrated NFC technology, you can easily touch your phone to purchase items, share business cards and so on. This paper gives a general overview of Near Field Communication (NFC) technology with a special focus on safety and security. First, an introduction is provided on how NFC works. The associated hardware structure, standard communication methods, and the relevant international standards for NFC are discussed. In the main section, this work examines the security and safety risks of NFC, summarizes built-in measures regarding security and safety and also suggests a principal protocol for safety integrated communication with NFC. Finally, this work shows some applications, with focus given to aid organizations, which would benefit greatly from the use of NFC technology.

Keywords: *Near Field Communication(NFC), Radio Frequency Identification(RFID), Radio Frequency(RF), Application Execution Environment (AEE), Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), Contactless Front-end (CLF), Subscriber Identity Module (SIM), Secure Memory Card(SMC), Universal Integrated Circuit Card(UICC).*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Near Field Communication (NFC) is a set of standards for mobile devices designed to establish radio communication with each other by being touched together or brought within a short distance. The NFC standard regulates a radio technology that allows two devices to communicate when they are in close proximity, usually no more than a few centimeters, allowing the secure exchange of information. NFC standards are based on different communications protocols and data exchange formats, and include also existing radio-frequency identification (RFID) standards such as the **ISO/IEC 14443** specific for identification cards, proximity cards and contactless integrated circuit cards. The coverage of various ISO standards ensures for NFC technology the global interoperability that makes the technology usable in different areas.

Fig.1 NFC Standards

From a technological perspective, NFC is also an extension also of the ECMA and ETSI standards, which describe the integration of a smart card with a terminal device. NFC devices allow writing and reading of information at a high speed (424Kbis / s) when they are placed in close proximity, creating a wireless connection, which is also compatible with widely used technologies such as Wi-Fi and Bluetooth. NFC is a Radio Frequency (RF) technology for communication over short distances up to about 10cm. It is mainly a logical advancement of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID). The history of RFID reaches back to the Second World War, where the British Air force tagged their planes with suitcase-sized devices to establish friend-enemy detection. The first commercial release came in the 1960's: 1 bit RFID for securing goods in shops, which is still widely used. In the 1990's RFID became more and more common e.g. for admission control systems or toll systems.

In 2002, NFC was developed by *NXP Semiconductors* and *Sony*. In general, NFC is compatible with existing RFID systems, but its architecture is different in principle. While RFID has only a reader - tag structure, an NFC device can be both reader and transmitter. In 2004, for better standardization the *NFC-Forum* was founded by the two developing companies. The forum now has about 140 members [17]. After this, the most NFC relevant standards were released as European Computer Manufacturers Association (ECMA) standards before becoming an ISO/IEC standard, by a procedure called *Fast-Track* [12]. The first NFC-compatible mobile phones were distributed by Samsung and Nokia in 2005. In the same year the first field trials in payment with NFC started in France [12]. The world's first commercial rollout of NFC was in Austria. *Mobilkom Austria*, *OEBB* and *Wiener Linien* placed about 450 NFC tags at vending machines to support the customer, in buying tickets for the railway and underground via SMS. For the near future, commercial use of NFC technology is expected to increase. This is due to the fact that three smart phone operating system / device manufacturers Apple (iPhone), Google (Android) and RIM (Blackberry) have announced plans to include NFC in their next products. Additionally, *MasterCard*, an international debit card company, is about to start its *PayPass*, an NFC based payment solution [15]

II.NFC TECHNOLOGY ARCHITECTURE

NFC is based on RFID technology at 13.56 MHz, with a typical operating distance up to 10 cm. The data exchange rate is up to 424 kilobits/s. Compared to other communication technology, the biggest advantage of NFC is it is quick and easy to use. The following graph compares NFC to other communication technologies.

Fig.2 Comparison of short-range communication technologies

A.Hardware architecture

NFC is an inductive coupled technology, the frequency of the RF field is 13.56MHz. The specified data rates (106kBit/s, 202kBit/s and 404kBit/s) are a consequence of the compatibility with the MIFARE (ISO/IEC 14443 Type A) and FeliCa (JISX 6319-4) RFID standards.

The main components of the NFC environment are [12]:

- **Host-Controller**

Application Execution Environment (AEE), the environment where the application rests e.g. mobile phone,

- **Secure Element**

Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), the secure environment where e.g. debit card data are stored,

- **NFC-Controller**

Contactless Front-end (CLF), the link between Host and NFC, with an interface to the *Secure Element*,

- **NFC-Antenna.**

1) NFC-Controller

The *NFC-Controller* is the link between *Air Interface*, *Host-Controller* and *Secure Element*. The *Host-Controller* is most likely a mobile device (e.g. a mobile phone, or a *smart car key*). Between *Host-* and *NFC-Controller* there are interfaces like Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI), Inter-Integrated Circuit (I2C) and Universal Serial Bus (USB) in use. For the communication with the *Secure Element* there are typically smartcard interfaces, the *NFC Wired Interface* or the *Single Wire Protocol* in use. The Controller works as modulator / demodulator between the analog *Air Interface* and other digital interfaces. The *NFC-Controllers* have integrated microcontrollers, which implement the low level services, so the exchange with the *Host- Controller* is limited to the application Data and some control commands [5, 12]. In some cases (e.g. *Card Emulation Mode* for payment applications with mobile phones) the *NFC-Controller* and the *Secure Element* should still work when the host is turned off or the battery is empty. For such cases, the interface between *NFC Controller* and *Secure Element* needs the possibility to power the *Secure Element* with the energy the *NFC-Controller* retrieves from the *Air Interface*. The *NFC Controller* can be connected to more than one *Secure Element* [12].

2) Secure Element

On most mobile devices (such as mobile phones) there is no way to store secure data directly. But for most NFC applications (e.g. payment and authentication solutions) such a storage system is essential. For such data, the storage needs to be secured from manipulation. Thus, it must be able to execute cryptographic functions and to implement a secure environment to execute security-relevant software. Smartcards usually implements these requirements [12]. To implement such a *Secure Element*, there are different possibilities, each with its own advantages and disadvantages [12].

- **Software without secure hardware.**

Software is the most flexible and independent solution, but software could not be optimally secured without the hardware as there is always the possibility that the unsecured hardware is manipulated.

- **Device integrated hardware.**

This is the most host dependent, but most reliable solution. The *Secure Element* is either a part of the host or is built in as its own chip. The communication with the element and the *NFC-Controller* works like a smartcard or over the *NFC Wired Interface*. The biggest disadvantage of this solution is, if the user changes the device, the provider of the secure service has to remove the data from the old device and to put it on the new one.

- **Changeable hardware.**

In most cases, this would be the best compromise between reliability, usability and costs. Because a hardware interface is needed to plug in the removable *Secure Element*, the production costs of the host device are higher. Such removable devices could be a Secure Memory Card (SMC), which combines the secure smartcard functions with a usual memory card function, or a Universal Integrated Circuit Card (UICC); for example in a mobile phone this is the Subscriber

Identity Module (SIM) card. On actual SIM cards there is only one out of 8 connectors free for use, so the *Single Wire Protocol* was introduced by European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI). While the SMC is usually owned by the user (he can change his data by himself), the SIM card of a mobile phone is owned by the network provider (the network provider must cooperate with the secure service provider). An NFC system implementing a *Secure Element* is often called shortly *Secure NFC*, this is misleading because only the data stored on the *Secure Element* is secured, not the whole NFC communication [7].

3) NFC Wired Interface

The *NFC Wired Interface (NFC-WI)* (by NXP Semiconductors also called S2C- Interface) is a two wire interface for data exchange between an *NFC-Controller* and the *Secure Element* and is standardized in ECMA-373: Near Field Communication Wired Interface (NFC-WI) [25]. It is shown in Figure 3.

It has two wires (Signal-In and Signal-Out) over which the NFC HF data is transferred directly. In this Interface the *NFC-Controller* is only the gateway between the *Secure Element* and the Air Interface. It is mostly used for *Card Emulation Mode*. Due to the direct NFC data transfer, this interface works on the NFC standard frequency of 13,56MHz and with the standard data rates: 106kBit/s, 202kBit/s and 404kBit/s [5, 12].

Fig.3 NFC Wired Interface

4) Single Wire Protocol

The *Single Wire Protocol* is standardized in the ETSI TS 102 613: UICC – Contactless Front-end (CLF) Interface; Part 1: Physical and data link layer characteristics [30] norm. It is shown in Figure 4.

It is a one wire interface over which the data and the energy is transferred. It was introduced, for the case when there is only one free connector on the usual 8 connector SIM cards. It is a Master-Slave-Interface, where the *NFC-Controller* is the master and the *Secure Element* is the slave. There is no connection between the *Secure Element* and the host, so all the data transfer must go through the *NFC Controller* by the use of Host Control Interface (HCI). The data transfer is managed by a High Level Data Link Control (HDLC) Protocol. Because the *Secure Element* drains its power from the *NFC-Controller* the *Single Wire Protocol* is an optimal solution for NFC-Services which have to work even if batterof the device is empty [5, 12].

Fig.4 Single Wire Protocol

II.SAFETY AND SECURITY

Safety is reliability regarding failures or an abstraction of avoidance of catastrophic consequences. Such consequences could be either physical injury of people or the damage of machinery. A quantitative definition can be given as the probability that the system will not exhibit a specified undesired behavior throughout a period of time. “*Functional safety is part of the overall safety that depends on a system or equipment operating correctly in response to its inputs.*” For a communication system, safety means that there is a guaranteed transfer of the data and given any disturbances there is a safe state where no catastrophic consequences can occur. *Security* is the prevention of unauthorized access and unauthorized manipulation of data. There is no quantitative definition possible. *Security* is categorized in three sections [16]:

- *Secrecy*: the measurements to prevent data from unauthorized access,
- *Integrity*: the measurements to prevent data from unauthorized changes,
- *Availability*: the percentage of time for which the data is accessible.

There are many ways to break the security of a system. However, in our further considerations we mainly concentrate on the risks given by the *Air Interface* of NFC.

A. Attacks on NFC systems

Figure 5 gives an overview of the possible attacks on a *NFC Reader / Writer* environment. In the other communication modes the situation is similar. The *Air Interface* is always the same and the participating NFC devices can always be manipulated either by the owner / user himself or without the owner’s knowledge by a hacker. Based on the motivation these attacks can be classified in four categories [2]:

- *Spying*: unauthorized access to information,
- *Deception*: deceive through wrong information,
- *Denial of Service* (DOS): compromise the availability of the NFC system,

- *Protection of privacy:*

“Because the attacker believes that his privacy is threatened by the RFID system, he protects himself by attacking the system.” [2]

Attacks on the backend of NFC devices (e.g. a network connection to verify secure keys) would enlarge this work too much, so they are of no concern in our further discussion. For an introduction into these themes, refer to [14].

B. Attacks on the tag

The attacks which could be performed on the Tag are:[5]

- *Destroy*

This is the simplest attack which could be used. Afterwards the tag is not able to communicate any longer with an NFC device. It could be destroyed mechanical, for example by cutting the connection to its antenna. Another way to destroy the tag is an overpowered electrical field on the tags working frequency, so that the electrical components would overload. Destroying the electrical circuits of the tag could also be done by placing the tag into a microwave oven. This attack would compromise the *availability* of an NFC system.

- *Remove*

In this attack, the tag is removed from the carrier object. The motivation for this could be a thief, who wants to smuggle the carrier object through the security checks without recognition. This attack would compromise the *availability* of an NFC system.

- *Shield*

This attack is only temporary and it could be done by placing the tag inside a metal box or a wrapping it in tinfoil. The inductive coupling is disturbed by high losses caused by eddy current induction inside the metal. This method could be used, for example, to pass automated toll checkpoints without recognition. The tag is not destroyed permanently. This attack would compromise the *availability* of an NFC system.

- *Clone*

In this attack the original tag is read and an exact copy is created. The complexity of this attack depends on the tag. A read-only tag which stores only a simple numeric ID can be cloned very easily. There are also simple solutions possible where the ID can be changed. The reader cannot decide if it is the original or the cloned tag. If some kind of certification is used, this attack would get more complex. This attack compromises the *secrecy* of an NFC system.

- *Falsify / Replace*

This attack overwrites the data of a tag or physically replaces it. Overwriting can be done easily if the original tag is a writeable tag without any security measures (or these measures are broken). The aim of this attack is to falsify the original tag, e.g. for phishing purposes. This attack compromises the *integrity* of an NFC system.

- *Tracking*

If a tag always uses the same unique ID for anti collision (or is a simple read only tag with a numeric ID) an attacker could track the tag easily. If the tag is always carried by the user, his movements could be tracked. This attack compromises the *secrecy* of an NFC system.

C. Attacks over the Air Interface

Due to the fact that the *Air Interface* is contactless, the attacks could be performed without physical access. That means that there are many possibilities for the attacker (or his equipment) to conceal his attacks. The actual known attacks over the *Air Interface* are [5, 7, 13].

- *High distance read:*

The attacker modifies an NFC device, to increase its range, so he can read tags from a safe distance. This is not as easy as it sounds at first. The attacker has to increase the energy of the High Frequency (HF) field, use an optimized antenna and handle the increasing noise in the communication. This attack compromises the *secrecy* of an NFC system.

- *Jamming:*

At *jamming* a sender blocks the NFC system by sending a disturbance signal on its frequency (13.56MHz). This sender must be either placed near the NFC system or use appropriate antennas and power rates. This attack compromises the *availability* of an NFC system.

- *Denial of Service:*

As there could be more than one NFC device / tag in range, an anti collision algorithm has to be performed to select the individual device to communicate with. The attacker generates collisions / answers for every possible device address and simulates the existence of a high amount of devices in range of the reader. The reader will now try to reach each of the simulated devices to disable them and communicate with the desired device. But in the case that the reader can never reach the simulated devices, the desired communication is blocked. This attack compromises the *availability* of an NFC system.

- *Man in the Middle:*

In a *Man in the Middle* attack two parties are tricked into a three party communication, without their knowledge. Instead of directly communication with each other they communicate through a third participant, who intercepts the messages between the other two. Thus he is able to modify data before sending it to the original receiver. An authentication system would not help, because the attacker can also intercept and set up one secure channel to the first party and a second secure channel to the second one. This attack compromises the *secrecy* and *integrity* of an NFC system.

- *Eavesdrop:*

Since NFC systems communicates over an open (accessible) medium (air) with electromagnetic waves, eavesdropping is a logical attack. Because the receiver of the attacker does not need the power of the active part of the communication for answering, he would be able to amplify weak signals received over a distance up to 30 - 40cm [8, 10]. [10] shows that producing such a eavesdrop equipment can be done at relatively low cost. This attack would compromise the *secrecy* of an NFC system.

- *Relay Attack:*

In this attack the invader uses another communication channel (relay) as an intermediary to increase the range. The attacker needs no physical access to the device, but only an antenna and the relay in reading range. The other, perhaps more conspicuous, devices could be far away. This attack would compromise the *secrecy* of an NFC system.

- *Data Modification:*

The attacker utilizes modulation of the signal to provide the receiver a valid but manipulated message. The feasibility of this attack depends highly on the coding mechanism for the modulation, and the data cannot be changed arbitrary but only to dominant states. This attack compromises the *integrity* of an NFC system.

- *Data Insertion:*

If the answering device needs a long time for its answer, the attacker could insert a message into the communication. This would be only successful if the transmission is finished, before the answering device starts with its answer. Otherwise the message would be corrupted. This attack compromises the *integrity* of an NFC system.

III.SECURITY MEASURES IN NFC

At the beginning of NFC there was no real focus on security measures due to its short range. Since there are concepts and plans to use NFC for payment and ticketing solutions, security became a high priority topic.

A. Measures against attacks

Most of the listed attacks could be prevented by using authentication and encryption methods. For example, eavesdropping would be possible, but if the data is encrypted, the attacker would not have use of it until he is able to decrypt it. A difficult attack to perform is the *Man in the Middle* attack. All three devices, have to be in one range, and so will disturb each other. To get a stable working communication, the attacker in the middle has to shield the connection between the other two devices. This would result in an attack if one of the parties is removed and replaced. Such an attack could be prevented by the use of authentication through a common, independent, trusted certification provider [12, 7].

Experiments [8, 10] show that a passive eavesdropping attack is possible up to a distance of 30 - 40cm. This limits the possibilities for an attacker to hide (himself or his equipment). But in a crowded scene like a full underground train at rush hour, the equipment placed in a bag would not be suspicious and the owners would not notice that their device has been read from a person walking by. To prevent data stored on the NFC device from unnoticed read by an attacker, it would be necessary to have an application on the host device which asks for permission (e.g. by entering a PIN code) before granting access to the data. As there are cases where the NFC function should also work even when the host device is short of energy or is switched off, there should also be the possibility to disable the NFC function. A simple mechanical switch would solve this requirement. Switching of the device would then prevent an attacker from skimming the NFC data while walking by [13].

After a synchronization phase both communication devices send randomized logical zeros and ones. Because NFC uses Amplitude Shift Keying Modulation, an eavesdropper would only know that both devices sent either a one or a zero at the same time or both have sent a different sign, but would not be able to determine which party has sent which sign. Each active communication party could retrieve the sign sent by the other one, knowing which randomized sign was sent by himself. This algorithm would work well, as long as the eavesdropper does not overhear the synchronization phase. On the NFC device the connection between *Secure Element* and host controller (application) should also be secured. This is needed to provide the security for the PIN and other codes which have to be transferred between them. Lastly, the user interaction should be done in a way which is not possible to intercept or clone by another application [12].

B. NFC Security standard series

The NFC-SEC: NFCIP-1 Security Services and Protocol [16] and NFC-SEC-01: NFC-SEC Cryptography Standard using ECDH and AES Reference were released in their first version in 2009 and are the standardized answer to the increasing requirement for security solutions in NFC systems.

NFC-SEC is the first part of the *NFC Security standard series*, and defines the common framework. This framework was created for securing the data exchange in *Peer to Peer Mode* and is placed above *NFCIP-1* (Physical and MAC layers) and below higher level protocols. It defines the necessary extensions to *NFCIP-1*: sequence protocols and other basic conditions. There are two services: the *Shared Secret Service* (SSE), which defines methods for establishing a shared secret (key) with application specific encryption methods, and the *Secure Channel Service* (SCH), which not only provides the connection set up, but also the establishing of a secure, encrypted communication path for the data messages [12, 16].

The other parts of the *NFC Security standard series*: *NFC-SEC-XX* defines specific cryptographic mechanisms. Together they define algorithms for *secure key exchange*, encoding and securing the data integrity and the sequence of the messages. Currently only *NFC-SEC-01* is officially available, which specifies the *Elliptic Curves Diffie-Hellman* (ECDH) algorithm for secure key exchange and the *Advanced Encryption Standard* (AES) (defined in ISO/IEC 1803-3) for encrypting the data.

C. Signature Record Type

NFC-SEC is targeted on two NFC devices communicating with each other in *Peer to Peer Mode*, so it gives no protection for an NFC device communicating with an NFC Forum Tag. This is where the Signature Record Type comes in. It gives the possibility to prove the authenticity of an NDEF record / message. *NFC Forum Tags* do not have significant security protection, they only have a write protection against overwriting with falsified data. Because usually they should be commonly readable, an encrypted data transfer would be an overkill. But they need a protection against replacing the tag (e.g. for phishing purposes), so the use of signatures would be necessary [13].

“However, a malicious third party could delete the signature record from the NDEF message or attach a new signature record to prevent the user from noticing any malicious change of content. It must be understood that the verification is only as trustworthy as the tools (signature algorithm, certificate, etc.) and processes (e.g., security policies) that are being used. These risks, along with the use of the Signature record, should be taken into consideration in the development of applications.” [13]

The *Signature Record Type* provides such a possibility to verify the integrity and authenticity of data through signatures. It is possible to sign one or more NDEF records inside an NDEF message with a *Signature Record*. The payload of the *Signature Record* consists of three fields:

- *Version field:*

Currently there is only one version of the record, so devices which implement the NFC Forums *Signature Record Type Definition - Technical Specification*, have to ignore any version other than 1 (0x01).

- *Signature field:*

This contains either the actual signature or a URI which points to the signature. The *Signature Record* always certifies the previous NDEF records of other type; if previous records should not be certified, an empty *Signature Record* has to be inserted.

- *Certificate Chain field:*

Finally, this contains the certificates necessary to authenticate the *Signature Record*. It contains a chain of up to 15 certificates, where the first one certifies the signature and the following certify the authenticity of up to 14 records.

IV. SAFETY MEASURES IN NFC

NFC was not explicitly designed for use in safety relevant applications, so not all of the above listed measures are an implicit part of the NFC standards. Since *functional safe* data transfers would most likely be

a two way communication, *Peer to Peer Mode* would be the mode of choice. In *Peer to Peer Mode* we have four layers where the measures could be placed. In NFC (lower three layers) there are two functions already integrated which could be used for creating a safe connection. The rest of the measures have to get implemented as a protocol in the application layer. The first NFC function which could be used is the *sequence integrity* of the *NFCSEC*[16] standard. It is situated among the MAC and the LLC layer. It provides a consistent sequence numbering where the sequence number is also secured to make changes in the numbering detectable. If the sequence of the messages is not correct the incorrect messages are rejected and not provided to the layers above. Upon this *time expectation* could be realized in the protocol. The second NFC function, could be the *connection-oriented Transport* of the LLC [21]. It is situated in the LLC layer. The *connection-oriented Transport* provides a sequenced message transport with guaranteed delivery through acknowledgment. This is done by numbering the data packets and sending back a Protocol Data Unit (PDU) for each message received. If sent messages are not acknowledged, an unexpected link disruption could be assumed. Once a connection is established, the LLC manages state information and receive buffers independently of other connections. The number of unacknowledged messages in the receive buffers before an unexpected link disruption is sensed could be configured. These two functions already allowing *sequence numbering*, and *time expectation* could easily be implemented on them. With these measures most of the errors defined in ISO/IEC 61784-3-1 are covered. There are three errors left to cover: *Corruption*, *Masquerade* and *Addressing*. Using a protocol which implements the *NFCSEC- 01* standards, would also cover the *Corruption*- (through encryption where a data integrity check is included) and the *Addressing*- (by establishing a secure connection with authentication) errors. So there is only the *Masquerade* error left by now, against whom the protection is the use of different redundancy checks in the channel and the protocol. Using a secured connection would provide the checks in the channel, so in the application protocol an additional data redundancy check needs to be implemented.

By building measures against the defined errors most of the requirements for a *functional safe* communication are covered. Securing the channel would prevent unintended or unauthorized reconfiguration of the devices over the air. Prevention from interference could be assured with the use of LLC, where established connections are independent from others. The calculation of the reaction time could go along with the measures for *time expectation*. The usage of *Peer to Peer Mode* and the *connection-oriented Transport* provides the publisher/subscriber and client/server connection. But the application protocol still needs to implement a check for the actual connection state. In case of a disrupted connection it must switch back to the fail safe state (not connected). The LLC state information and the *time expectation* measure should be helpful in implementing these connection checks. Finally, it should be possible to create a *functional safe* connection, with an application specific protocol implementing these extensions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an overview of NFC technologies and possible underlying applications. NFC and RFID techniques are discussed. Also, the principal hardware design and the need for a *Secure Element* to store data are presented. Finally, the chapter gives an overview of the most relevant NFC standards. It examines the possible risks and attacks NFC systems are exposed to. Along necessary security measures are shown. In parallel, NFC is analyzed in relation to functional safety. In principle, NFC was not designed to provide safe communication. However, with help of underlying security measures and an application specific protocol also a functional safe communication according to ISO/IEC 61784-3-1 could be established. Besides payment solutions and applications within the area of ambient assisted living (e.g. tele-care and monitoring), emergency systems have been identified as future targets of interest for NFC technology.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sebastian Dunnebeil, Felix Kobler, Philip Koene, Jan Marco Leimeister, and Helmut Krcmar. Encrypted NFC Emergency Tags Based on the German Telematics Infrastructure. Hagenberg, Austria, February 2011.
- [2] FIA Foundation. Rescue sheet. <http://www.rescue-sheet.info>
- [3] Google wallet. <http://www.google.com/wallet>.
- [4] Ernst Haselsteiner and Klemens Breitfuß. Security in Near Field Communication (NFC) - Strengths and Weaknesses. RFIDSec, 2006.
- [5] Z. Kfir and A. Wool. Picking Virtual Pockets using Relay Attacks on Contactless Smartcard. First International Conference on Security and Privacy for Emerging Areas in Communications Networks.
- [6] Hermann Kopetz. REAL-TIME SYSTEMS, Design Principles for Distributed Embedded Applications. Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2002.
- [7] Josef Langer and Michael Roland. Anwendungen und Technik von Near Field Communication (NFC). Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2010.
- [8] Gerald Madlmayr, Josef Langer, Christian Kantner, and Josef Scharinger. NFC Devices: Security and Privacy. pages 642–647, March 2008.
- [9] Gerald Madlmayr, Josef Langer, Christian Kantner, Josef Scharinger, and Ingrid Schaumuller-Bichl. Risk Analysis of Over-the-Air Transactions in an NFC Ecosystem.
- [10] NFC Forum. About the NFC forum. <http://www.nfc-forum.org/aboutus>
- [11] NFC Forum. NFC Data Exchange Format (NDEF) - Technical Specification, 2006.
- [12] NFC Forum. NFC Record Type Definition (RTD) - Technical Specification, 2006.
- [13] NFC Forum. Signature Record Type Definition - Technical Specification, 2010.
- [14] Norm ECMA-352. Near Field Communication Interface and Protocol -2(NFCIP-2), 2010.
- [15] Norm ECMA-373. Near Field Communication Wired Interface (NFC-WI),2006.
- [16] Norm ECMA-385. NFC-SEC: NFCIP-1 Security Services and Protocol, 2010.
- [17] Norm ISO/IEC 61508. Functional safety of electric / electronic / programmable electronic safety-related systems., 1998.
- [18] Norm ISO/IEC 61784-3-1. Functional safety field buses - Additional specifications